

Two different Late Ediacaran series in SW Iberian Massif: Geochemical and isotopic (Sm-Nd) evidences

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The Iberian Massif represents the southwestern branch of the Variscan Orogen, formed during the assembly of Pangea. It contains several sutures generated during the long convergence and collision between Gondwana and Laurussia, as well as an excellent stratigraphic record of the Ediacaran and Paleozoic sedimentary series deposited in different paleogeographic locations along the paleomargin of Gondwana. The current juxtaposition of distant sections of the Gondwanan margin, is in general a consequence of the Variscan convergence. In the SW of the Iberian Massif, the nature of the boundary between an autochthonous domain (Central Iberian Zone) and the allochthonous domains (Ossa-Morena Complex), is under discussion. Previous interpretations based on U-Pb geochronology of detrital zircons have suggested that the Ediacaran and Early Paleozoic sedimentary series located in the Central Iberian Zone, were deposited along the Gondwana margin more to the East than the equivalent series of the Ossa-Morena Complex. Since the geochemistry and isotopic sources of the contemporary siliciclastic series located at the Central Iberian Zone and the Ossa-Morena Complex have not yet been compared, we use major and trace elements geochemical data and Sm-Nd isotopic tracers to constrain the nature of the boundary between both domains.

This research compares the whole rock geochemical data of the Ediacaran siliciclastic series (565 Ma) located in nearby domains at both sides of the Central Iberian Zone – Ossa-Morena Complex boundary, i.e. the southernmost sector of Central Iberian Zone and the northernmost part of the Ossa-Morena Complex, designated as the Obejo-Valsequillo Domain. Equivalent series have been traditionally referred to as Lower Alcludian Series and Serie Negra, respectively. The major and trace element geochemistry and the Sm-Nd isotopic data of the siliciclastic rocks presented in the Serie Negra and Lower Alcludian suggest deposition in an active margin setting. Nevertheless, the Serie Negra shows a range of higher negative values for the $\epsilon\text{Nd}_{(0)}$ and $\epsilon\text{Nd}_{(565)}$ (-9.8 to -20.5 and -4.0 to -13.9, respectively) relative to the Lower Alcludian values ($\epsilon\text{Nd}_{(0)}$ and $\epsilon\text{Nd}_{(565)}$ ranging -6.4 to -8.8 and -1.4 to -3.0, respectively). Therefore, TDM values of the Serie Negra are significantly older (1421-2040 Ma) than those of the Lower Alcludian (1256-1334 Ma), which would situate its source areas in the periphery of a cratonic region likely in the realm of the West African Craton, close to the Ediacaran magmatic arc. The different Nd model ages indicate that the source areas for the Lower Alcludian were isotopically younger than those for the Serie Negra, which would suggest deposition at distant sections within the Gondwana margin. According to these data, the boundary between the Central Iberian Zone and the Ossa-Morena Complex (Obejo-Valsequillo Domain) may represent a zone with significant tectonic transport. Variscan thrusting developed in a dextral convergence setting is found as the main contributor to the current juxtaposition of Ediacaran series along this boundary. This conclusion can be very likely extrapolated to some other equivalent boundaries throughout the Variscan Orogen.

Keywords: Ediacaran series; Central Iberia-Ossa Morena boundary; Isotopic geochemistry.